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Block-Scale Steganography in Color Images

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Abstract

Today, ensuring the secure transmission of data over the internet is of great importance, as there is a risk that original data may be accessed by unauthorized third parties. The aim of this study is to develop a method that enhances data security by using the steganography technique to protect confidential and personal information from unauthorized access. Steganography is a technique in which ordinary images are used as carriers to store information in a concealed manner. In this method, the sender must select an appropriate carrier image, message content, and encryption key when determining the message to be hidden. The primary goal of steganography is to ensure secure data storage without introducing any noticeable changes to the image in which the message is embedded. Considering the studies conducted in the literature on data hiding, RGB image data and the wavelet transform—one of the multi-scale methods developed in recent years—constitute the focus of this research.

In this study, the data to be concealed is an RGB image, which is divided into blocks using a matrix-column-based approach. A cover image was selected for each block, and these blocks were embedded into the cover images using the Haar wavelet transform. Finally, the blocks obtained from the cover images were combined to reconstruct the secret image. The Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index Method (SSIM) values were examined to compare the original secret image and the reconstructed image.

Keywords: Steganography, Wavelet transform, Color image.

1. Introduction

With the rapid advancement of technology, taking security measures in response to new developments in our lives has become an unavoidable necessity. The security of online transactions, which we frequently use in our daily lives, cannot always be fully guaranteed. When using the internet, we exchange data and frequently share personal information in the process. To ensure that this information reaches the recipient without being read or altered in any way, we may sometimes need to take individual security measures, depending on the value of the information. This study examines

personal security measures that can be taken to prevent third-party monitoring or modification of images sent or stored over the internet.

Steganography is a technique for encryptedly hiding information within normal images. The goal of steganography is to ensure that changes to the carrier image caused by embedding a secret image are visually unnoticeable. If the existence of secret messages is successfully concealed, unauthorized individuals or groups cannot detect the secret, and the secret cannot become a target for attack. Steganography can be applied to various formats, such as text, images, audio, and video. In this research, the steganography technique was used specifically on images.

2. Mathematical Framework

Steganography is a technique that protects confidential information by embedding it within a medium such as images or audio. The medium carrying the confidential data is called "stego." The primary goal of steganography is to conceal the transmitted information in a way that makes its presence unnoticeable; the better the data is concealed, the more secure the information is. However, for the data to be meaningful, the recipient must know both the transmission channel and the information needed to decrypt it; therefore, in steganography, it is essential to protect how the data will be transmitted and decrypted.

Our proposed method ensures the security of the image data to be hidden by embedding it within other selected images. All images are treated as color images. Because the images are matrices, they can be divided into any number of rows and/or columns. The resulting cover image blocks are embedded within the selected cover images as many times as the number of blocks. Embedding is performed using the Discrete Wavelet Transform. The Discrete Wavelet Transform is a transform that divides the image into four sub-bands, allowing for independent embedding, and provides high visual quality for stego images. In the transform domain, the embedding is performed using transformed coefficients rather than direct intensity values. This way, the structure of the cover images is not distorted, but it is not perceptible to human vision. Even if this embedding, which can be detected by computers and removed from the cover image, is detected, the secret image can not be accessed without obtaining all blocks and determining their locations.

2.1. Discrete Haar Wavelet Transform

The discrete wavelet transform is an application of the wavelet transform formulated in equation 1. ω is a continuous function, j is a scaler, and k is a sliding parameter. The equation representing ω is as follows:

$$\omega_{j,k}(t) = 2^{-\frac{j}{2}}\omega(2^{-j}t - k) \quad (1)$$

Wavelet series expansion maps a function of a continuous variable to a series of coefficients. If the expanded function is discrete, the resulting coefficients are called discrete wavelet transforms. There are three discrete wavelet transforms (1-D DWT, 2-D DWT, and 3-D DWT), the first being the one-dimensional discrete wavelet transform. The multi resolution formulations of the 1-D DWT, scaling, and wavelet functions are given in Equations 2 and 3.

$$\theta_{j,m,n}(x,y) = 2^{\frac{j}{2}}\theta(2^jx - m, 2^jy - n) \quad (2)$$

$$\vartheta_{j,m,n}^i(x,y) = 2^{\frac{j}{2}}\vartheta^i(2^jx - m, 2^jy - n) \quad (3)$$

Here i = directed wavelets, j = arbitrary initial scale, m and n determine the location of the scaling function.

The discrete wavelet transform is used to transform image pixels into wavelets. Various encodings are applied to the frequency-based images obtained using this technique. The multi-level wavelet decomposition is applied to the original selected image (Figure 1(a)). Applying the 1-D DWT single-level decomposition of Figure 1(b) to the original image will produce the result shown in Figure 1(c).

Figure 1. Multilevel Wavelet Decomposition.

The advantage of discrete wavelet transforms over other transform methods is that they retain frequency and position information. The DWT algorithm achieves this; it requires matrix data to perform the transform.

By preserving frequency position, signal denoising, data compression, and coding of various DWT types, such as 2D DWT, have been achieved.

Equation 4 shows the 2D function of the Haar matrix associated with Haar wavelets.

$$H_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

In this case, the transformation is applied to each 2x2 matrix. When the 1-D transformation is applied to each row, the result of this transformation is used as input to transform each column to obtain the DHWT. The results of the 2-D transformation using the 2x2 matrix are shown in Equation 5.

$$DHWT(X) = DHWT \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} a+b+c+d & a-b+c-d \\ a+b-c-d & a-b-c+d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} W_X^{LL} & W_X^{HL} \\ W_X^{LH} & W_X^{HH} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Here W_X^{LL} are horizontal and vertical low pass, W_X^{HL} are horizontal high pass and vertical low pass, W_X^{LH} are horizontal low pass and vertical high pass, and W_X^{HH} are horizontal and vertical high pass transform components [1].

3. Applications and Implications

All images in this study are 24-bit deep and in RGB format. The secret image used is 720 x 576. The image we call the secret image and assume we need to protect is shown in Figure 2.

Cover images were selected in different file types, including BMP, JPEG, and PNG, to demonstrate their suitability for various image types, with 24-bit depth, different sizes, and different image types. The idea behind this study is to divide the image to be hidden into the desired number of blocks and embed the same number of blocks within the cover image. The images we will use as cover images and embed the blocks of the secret image are shown in Figure 3.

The program used during application development is the MATLAB (R2018b) package program. The decomposition and Wavelet Transform and embedding operations applied to the visual data used during the application and development phase of the method were performed by writing appropriate codes in the MATLAB package program.

The Discrete Wavelet Transform is a transform that divides an image into four sub-bands, allowing for independent embedding, providing high visual quality for stego images. In the transform domain, the

embedding is performed using transformed coefficients rather than direct intensity values. This way, the structure of the cover images remains intact, yet remains invisible to the human visual system.

Figure 2.Secret Image

Figure 3. Cover Images

The secret image is considered as a matrix, as given in equation 6, and divided into equal parts as the number of blocks to be divided.

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & \cdots & a_{1720} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{5761} & \cdots & a_{576720} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & \cdots & a_{1120} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{5761} & \cdots & a_{576120} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_{1121} & \cdots & a_{1240} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{576121} & \cdots & a_{576240} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_{1241} & \cdots & a_{1360} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{576241} & \cdots & a_{576360} \end{pmatrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} a_{1361} & \cdots & a_{1480} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{576361} & \cdots & a_{576480} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_{1481} & \cdots & a_{1600} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{576481} & \cdots & a_{576600} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_{1601} & \cdots & a_{1720} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{576601} & \cdots & a_{576720} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

In the proposed method, the image is divided into six blocks shown in Figure 4 with the matrix logic given in Equation 7.

Figure 4. The Secret Image is Separated into Blocks.

By applying a level-1 Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) to the cover images using the MATLAB application, the sub-bands were obtained separately for each image as shown in Figure 5, and the blocks of the secret image were embedded into the sub-bands of the cover images. The resulting embedded images are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Wavelet Sub-bands of the First Cover Image.

Figure6. Cover Images with Embedded Shares.

4. Results and Discussion

By applying the Inverse Wavelet Transform to the obtained embedded cover images, the blocks of the secret image were extracted from the sub-bands in which they were embedded. Figure 7 shows the version of the first block obtained from the first cover image.

Figure7. Extraction of the Block from the Embedded Sub-band.

The shares obtained by extracting all the blocks from the sub-bands in which they were embedded using the Inverse Wavelet Transform are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Blocks Extracted from the Sub-bands.

As seen in Figure 8, the sizes of the blocks extracted from the sub-bands differ from each other. This is because the cover images selected have different dimensions. In the embedding process, the key we possess corresponds to the scaling size. If the scaling size is unknown, the images cannot be combined. The shares obtained solely from the extracted sub-bands do not yield a meaningful result. After applying the scaling process, the shares are resized to match the actual block dimensions, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure9. Scaled Versions of the Blocks Extracted from the Sub-bands.

By combining the obtained shares, an image close to the secret image is reconstructed. The resulting image is presented in Figure 10.

Figure10. Reconstructed Secret Image.

The Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index Method (SSIM) values were examined between the obtained image and the original secret image. A PSNR value greater than 20 is considered acceptable, and in our application, it was measured as 22.1010. The SSIM, a perception-based method that considers image degradation as a change in structural information, is measured on a scale from 0 to 1. In our application, the SSIM value was obtained as 0.8468, indicating that there is no significant difference between the secret image and the reconstructed image.

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